

Exploring the Relationship Between Residence and Preschool Location

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Summary

To date, there appears to be minimal research analysing spatial variation in travel to preschool on a large scale, such as a city. This work aimed to explore where children travelled to preschool across Glasgow, Scotland, and the relationship between distance and school density, socioeconomic status and developmental difficulties. It was found that distance travelled to preschool is most influenced by the number of schools in the area and the least deprived children are the most likely to leave their electoral ward to travel to school.

KEYWORDS: travel, preschool, early childhood, deprivation

1. Background

A variety of considerations may lead a parent or caregiver to choose a school outside of the local area. This impacts the physical and social environments a child is exposed to (Sharkey, P. and Faber, J.W., 2014).

Talen (2001) found that the distribution of distance to school varied by counties in West Virginia, with shorter distances in more urban areas and no obvious association with socioeconomic status. A recent study in Beijing assessed spatial variations in travel to primary and secondary school (Xiang, Gould and Stillwell, 2021). Children with high incomes travelled the furthest. Areas with higher density of schools and area deprivation were associated with shorter distance.

The role of geographic distance may vary by national educational systems (McLean, C., Naumann, I. and Koslowski, A., 2017). Despite this, there has been comparatively less research on travel to preschool. Distances travelled from home to preschool varied by establishment in a comparison of four preschools in Gloucestershire. Overall, travel distances were smaller in areas of greater deprivation (Oxford, L. and Pollock, J., 2015).

To date, there appears to be minimal research analysing variation in distance to preschool across a city. This work aimed to explore how the distance travelled to preschool varied across Glasgow and the relationship between distance and school density and socioeconomic status, and developmental difficulties.

2. Methodology

The ChiME study (Child Mental Health in Education) is a collaboration between the Universities of Glasgow, Aberdeen, Strathclyde, Edinburgh and Glasgow City Council Education Services. During 2010-2017 routine data collected by the council for local authority preschools was linked to individual developmental and demographic data. All children living in Glasgow who were attending a local authority preschool or private preschool with funded places were eligible. In total, 37,491 children from

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181 preschools were included.

Exploratory data analysis and data visualisations were conducted in R version 4.0.1.

2.1 Geographical Data

Residential postcodes were located within the 21 electoral wards of the Glasgow council area (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1 Glasgow Electoral Wards Multi-member wards in Glasgow used from 2007 to 2017. 1 Anderston/City, 2 Baillieston, 3 Calton, 4 Canal, 5 Craigton, 6 Drumchapel/Annie'sland, 7 East Centre, 8 Garscadden/Scotstounhill, 9 Govan, 10 Greater Pollok, 11 Hillhead, 12 Langside, 13 Linn, 14 Maryhill/Kelvin, 15 Newlands/Auldburn, 16 North East, 17 Partick West, 18 Pollokshields, 19 Shettleston, 20 Southside Central, 21 Springburn.

2.2 Variables

Preschool Location - Postcode and electoral ward of the 164 participating preschools were identified through the 2013 Childcare Information Services in Glasgow database accessed through the Urban Big Data Centre.

The relationship between residential postcode and preschool location was examined through the distance between the longitude and latitude associated with the postcode and for the preschool. Distance was calculated using the Haversine (Great Circle) Distance. As distances were skewed, they are expressed as medians and interquartile ranges (IQR).

Ward Size - Shapefiles for electoral wards included the size for each polygon and calculated to square kilometre.

Deprivation – In the absence of household data, deprivation was categorised using the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD) as a proxy for household socioeconomic status. SIMD quintiles were calculated to reflect relative deprivation within Glasgow rather than for the whole of Scotland.

Developmental Difficulties - Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ) was completed for all children in the ChiME study. The total SDQ score reflects emotional symptoms, conduct problems, hyperactivity/inattention and peer problems.

3. Results

1,894 children were excluded from analysis as the location of their preschool could not be identified. Missingness varied by preschool and ward. For example, 294 children who were excluded lived in Hillhead compared to 30 who lived in Baillieston. And the number excluded per school ranged from 1 to 319.

The final sample was 35,597 children. A summary of the number preschools identified in each ward and number of children living or attending preschool in the ward is shown in **Table 1**.

Table 1 Number of Children and Preschools in each Ward

Ward	Living in Ward	Attending Preschool in Ward	Number of Preschools
Anderston/City	838 (4.01%)	1427 (4.01%)	15
Baillieston	1995 (5.6%)	2660 (7.47%)	13
Calton	1304 (3.66%)	1463 (4.11%)	4
Canal	1809 (5.08%)	1911 (5.37%)	9
Craigton	1959 (5.50%)	2046 (5.75%)	8
Drumchapel/Anniesland	2162 (6.07%)	2295 (6.45%)	10
East Centre	1986 (5.58%)	1542 (4.33%)	6
Garscadden/Scotstounhill	1807 (5.08%)	708 (1.99%)	2
Govan	1804 (5.07%)	1838 (5.16%)	7
Greater Pollok	2224 (6.25%)	1528 (4.29%)	8
Hillhead	808 (2.27%)	1255 (3.53%)	6
Langside	1229 (3.45%)	3679 (10.34%)	7
Linn	1966 (5.52%)	1604 (4.51%)	11
Maryhill/Kelvin	1829 (5.14%)	1343 (3.77%)	8
Newlands/Auldburn	1498 (4.21%)	1527 (4.29%)	7
North East	2513 (7.06%)	2298 (6.46%)	9
Partick West	1300 (3.65%)	1373 (3.86%)	8
Pollokshields	1412 (3.97%)	757 (2.13%)	4
Shettleston	1787 (5.02%)	801 (2.25%)	6
Southside Central	2123 (5.96%)	2155 (6.05%)	9
Springburn	1244 (3.49%)	1387 (3.90%)	7

The median distance travelled to preschool was 716.79m (with interquartile range of 385.47m – 1,428.87m). The maximum distance travelled was 17,376.52m. There was wide variation in distance travelled between wards and within wards. Garscadden/Scotstounhill had the highest travel distance while those in Anderston/City had the shortest distance as shown in **Figure 2**.

Median distance travelled had a moderate, negative correlation with the number of schools in the ward ($r=-0.44$). There was a very small, positive correlation between median distance travelled and size of the home electoral ward ($r=0.10$), the smallest wards had the lowest median distance travelled on average. At an individual level, there was no relationship between developmental difficulties and distance to preschool ($r=-0.03$). There was a weak negative correlation between deprivation and distance to preschool ($r= -0.12$).

Figure 2 Median Distance Travelled to Preschool. Lat (latitude) and Long (longitude)

Higher travel distances were largely for children who left their ward. Two thirds of the sample (66.6%) attended a preschool in the same electoral ward as they lived. This varied across electoral wards (Figure 3).

Overall, children appeared to be more likely to stay in their ward in more central, north and south west regions of the city. Over 85% of children leave their wards in Drumchapel/Annie'sland and less than 40% leave neighbouring Garscadden/Scotstounhill. The median distance from those who left their ward was 1,769m compared to 525m in those who stayed.

Figure 3 Proportion of children who stay in their ward. Lat (latitude) and Long (longitude)

The route between the residential and preschool ward for those who leave is shown in **Figure 4**. There were 311 routes identified. Langside was the most travelled to ward for preschool, with a large volume of children from nearby wards such as Linn and Greater Pollok attending. There was also a high volume in children travelling from Shettleston and East Centre to neighbouring Baillieston.

Figure 4 The relationship between the residential and preschool ward for those who leave

On average, the proportion of children who stay in the ward was highest among children in the least deprived quintile (5) and lowest in the most deprived quintile (1) as shown in **Figure 5**. For example, none of the children who travelled to Langside were among the 40% most deprived in Glasgow.

Figure 5 Proportion of children who stay in their ward by Deprivation

4. Discussion

On average, preschool children travel <800m, which is considered within walking distance of their preschool when they stay in their ward. This exploratory study finds that the number of schools in the ward was strongly related to distance travelled. Areas with fewer preschools saw children more likely to leave their ward. There was a relationship between whether a child leaves a ward and their socioeconomic status whereby children in most deprived groups are the least likely to leave.

5. Acknowledgements

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Biographies

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